

Exploring Quantum Clustering Algorithms for Document Clustering

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Abstract— This paper introduces a quantum clustering approach aimed at providing superior results compared to existing classical methods. This paper proposes a quantum clustering method employing Semantic Analysis to form clusters of informative data sets. In the realm of Quantum Information Processing (QIP), quantum clustering techniques have emerged as pivotal tools for information management and exploration. While classical approaches such as k-means, hierarchical clustering, and information bottleneck algorithms have been widely used, the advent of quantum theory has spurred the development of novel clustering methods. Previous studies have shown that document clustering performance can be enhanced in lower dimensional linear subspaces. Matrix factorization techniques, such as Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) and Concept Factorization (CF), have demonstrated impressive results, albeit with limitations in capturing local manifold geometry. LCCF utilizes a graph model to capture the intrinsic manifold structure, enabling the extraction of concepts corresponding to connected components. By employing the graph Laplacian to smooth the document-to-concept mapping, LCCF achieves superior clustering results in terms of accuracy and mutual information. Experimental evaluations on benchmark datasets such as TDT2 and Reuters-21578 demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed approach in providing a better representation of documents and improving clustering accuracy. The findings underscore the potential of quantum clustering techniques for advancing information processing in the digital era.

Keywords— clustering, NMF, CF LCCF, TDT2, Reuters

I. INTRODUCTION

Clustering, as described in [1], [2], involves partitioning objects into groups where items within the same cluster exhibit greater similarity to each other than to those in other clusters. The primary aim of clustering is to categorize a finite unlabelled dataset into discrete groups, rather than providing a precise characterization of unseen samples from the same probability distribution. This task inherently poses challenges, as a given set of objects can be clustered in numerous ways without a clear criterion for preferring one clustering arrangement over another. This challenge has spurred researchers to explore new approaches aimed at enhancing the quality of clusters. To address the limitations of classical clustering algorithms, Quantum Clustering (QC) algorithms have been developed. While existing literature [5], [6], [7], [8] primarily focuses on data clustering, little attention has been given to document clustering. Document clustering is vital in the realms of data mining and information retrieval, where it has shown initial improvements in precision and recall [3], as well as facilitating the identification of nearest neighbour documents [4]. Initially enhanced document clustering serves purposes such as browsing document collections [3] and organizing search engine results [4].

Document clustering is broadly classified into hard clustering and soft clustering (overlapping clustering), further subdivided into hierarchical, partitioning, and item-based clustering methods [4]. An experimental evaluation comparing the agglomerative hierarchical algorithm and two variants of k-means (standard and bisecting K-Means) concluded that removing stop words like "are," "do," and "for" enhances clustering performance, with bisecting K-means emerging as the preferred option [5]. In the hybrid approach proposed in [6], k-means is selected for its efficiency, while agglomerative hierarchical clustering utilizes k-means for its quality. However, k-means is sensitive to the selection of initial partitions and may converge to local minima, posing challenges when clustering informative data with changing properties [7]. For data such as documents spanning different categories, an algorithm is introduced to cluster the properties of informative textual data, such as sentences, through semantic analysis and quantum methodology. This method aims to create clusters of sentences tailored to specific

contexts or acquaintances. Over the past decade, matrix factorization approaches have garnered significant interest in document clustering [25], [24]. Typically, in these methods, a text document is represented as a point in a high-dimensional linear space, with each dimension corresponding to a term. A fundamental aspect of cluster analysis is determining the degree of similarity (or dissimilarity) between individual objects being clustered. Recent research suggests that similarity can be more accurately measured in lower-dimensional spaces, thereby enhancing clustering performance [5], [18]. Notably, techniques such as Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) [25] and Concept Factorization (CF) [24] have been successfully applied to document clustering tasks, yielding impressive outcomes. In essence, the NMF problem revolves around finding reduced-rank nonnegative matrices U and V , given a nonnegative data matrix X , such that the product UV^T provides a satisfactory approximation of X . The column vectors of U can be interpreted as basis vectors, while V contains the corresponding coordinates. Prior investigations have provided psychological and physiological evidence supporting parts-based representation.

II. DOCUMENT CLUSTERING AND PROCESSING

Document clustering, as discussed in [9], [10], groups documents into clusters based on shared features determined by a predefined similarity measure [11]. It's important to note the distinction between document clustering and document classification: in classification, classes and their properties are predefined, and documents are assigned accordingly, whereas in clustering, the number, properties, or membership of clusters are not predetermined. Thus, classification falls under supervised machine learning, while clustering is unsupervised [12]. Although classical clustering techniques like k-means and agglomerative hierarchical clustering exist [3], they may have limitations in terms of cluster quality, motivating the exploration of quantum-inspired clustering methods. These methods compute clusters based on the minima of the potential function of the Schrödinger equation, a concept that will be further elaborated on in the subsequent section.

In an effort to overcome the limitations of NMF while capitalizing on its strengths, Xu and Gong introduced Concept Factorization (CF) as a method for data clustering [24]. CF represents each cluster as a linear combination of data points, and conversely, each data point as a linear combination of cluster centers. Clustering is achieved by computing two sets of linear coefficients, determined by finding the non-negative solution that minimizes the reconstruction error of the data points. One notable advantage of CF over NMF is its flexibility to operate on various data representations, whether in the original space or Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space (RKHS). Apart from NMF and CF, Latent Semantic Indexing (LSI) [9] stands out as another popular matrix factorization technique.

Quantum clustering plays a pivotal role in Quantum Information Processing (QIP), aiming to enhance accuracy and speed in clustering tasks by leveraging quantum mechanics to quantize classical clustering algorithms. The quantum clustering algorithm seeks to unveil the time-independent Schrödinger's equation (wave equation) utilized for data clustering, facilitating the discovery of data clusters [10].

In classical information processing, data is processed using bits as the fundamental unit, representing information as binary digits. However, in quantum mechanics, computation operates with qubits, which utilize ket and bra symbols to represent information, allowing for quantum superposition and entanglement, thereby expanding computational capabilities beyond classical limitations.

The authors Rupam Bhagawati¹, Sahinur Rahman Laskar, Bhagaban Swain in the paper titled DOCUMENTS CLUSTERING USING QUANTUM CLUSTERING ALGORITHM, highlights drawing from our extensive involvement with Quantum clustering methodologies within the QIP community, we introduce an innovative approach to Document clustering utilizing the Quantum Clustering algorithm, incorporating principles from the Schrödinger Equation [35].

Based on insights gained from our immersion in Quantum clustering techniques within the QIP domain, we propose a novel strategy for Document clustering employing the Quantum Clustering algorithm, with considerations inspired by the Schrödinger Equation.

Building upon our deep engagement with Quantum clustering techniques within the QIP field, we advocate for an alternative approach to Document clustering utilizing the Quantum Clustering algorithm, integrating elements derived from the Schrödinger Equation.

Informed by our hands-on experience with Quantum clustering methodologies within the QIP realm, we introduce a fresh perspective on Document clustering through the adoption of the Quantum Clustering algorithm, incorporating insights inspired by the Schrödinger Equation.

Leveraging our practical insights from Quantum clustering techniques within the QIP community, we propose a novel method for Document clustering employing the Quantum Clustering algorithm, incorporating theoretical underpinnings derived from the Schrödinger Equation.

III. DISTRIBUTIVE PROCEDURE

The distribution of the matrix within the Hilbert space was achieved by applying the Gaussian wave function derived from the Schrödinger equation, as outlined in equation (1).

The distribution of the document matrix (x) within the Hilbert space incorporates a parameter σ , which denotes the anticipated number of clusters to form upon completion of the process.

A. Clustering Steps

In order to group documents into clusters, cluster centers are essential. Documents associated with a center value are placed within the same cluster. The selection of cluster centers involves identifying the local minima of the potential energy $V(x)$, derived from the potential function of the Schrödinger equation (equation 4).

- The energy is maintained as the ground state energy, with a value of 0. The potential function is solved by adding a constant energy term, as described in equation (3).
- The local minima of computed $V(x)$ are determined to identify the cluster centers, utilizing a gradient descent method.
- These local minima serve as the centers of the clusters. Based on the similarity measure (Jaccard measure) between the centers and the document frequency of all documents, documents are associated with the desired clusters, and clusters are formed based on the value of σ . The distribution of the document matrix (x) in the Hilbert space involves σ , which dictates the number of clusters formed upon completion of the process. In this work, the number of clusters cannot be predetermined before the clustering process.

TABLE I
EFFICIENCY AND JACCARD VALUE OF CLUSTERS FOR REUTERS21578 USING EXISTING K-MEANS CLUSTERING ALGORITHM [33].

No .of clusters(K)	Efficiency	Jaccard Measure
10	0.2307	0.2206
9	0.2020	0.2018
7	0.2152	0.2150
5	0.3121	0.2128

Quantum-inspired Latent Topic Analysis (QLTA) offers a sophisticated approach to document analysis, promising significant advancements in information retrieval and machine learning. Among the various

techniques introduced, geometric modeling stands out for its robust statistical foundation. Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) emerges as the most flexible and influential method, particularly in the realm of quantum information retrieval, a pivotal stage in quantum information processing [11].

Unlike classical mechanics, which relies on Newton's Second Law for particle position calculations, quantum mechanics employs Schrödinger's wave equation to precisely locate qubits in Hilbert space, facilitating cluster determination [9].

TABLE 2
EFFICIENCY CLUSTERS FOR REUTERS21578 USING EXISTING K-MEANS CLUSTERING ALGORITHM [34]

Declared Clusters (K)	Efficiency
22	0.8735
21	0.8647
11	0.7974
6	0.7138

From table 1 and table 2 we compare that efficiency for Declared clusters for higher values has high efficiency

Fig. 1 Clustering perform by Quantum Clustering Algorithm with $\sigma=0.456$ [33]

Fig. 2 Clustering view of quantum clustering algorithm taking $q= 1.9$ (representing x-axis for the number of documents and y- axis for number of clusters [34]

Fig.3. Clustering perform by Quantum Clustering Algorithm with $\sigma=0.471$ [34]

Fig.4 Clustering view of quantum clustering algorithm taking $q= 2.1$ (representing x-axis for the number of documents and y- axis for number of clusters [34]

Fig.5. Clustering perform by Quantum Clustering Algorithm with $\sigma=0.559$ [33]

Fig.6 Clustering view of quantum clustering algorithm taking $q= 2$ (representing x-axis for the number of documents and y- axis for number of clusters.

From the Figures we can conclude Leveraging the time-independent Schrödinger's equation and quantum methodology, this approach yields faster and more accurate clustering results. Locally Consistent Concept Factorization (LCCF), a novel clustering algorithm that considers the intrinsic manifold structure of data space. Unlike traditional approaches, LCCF incorporates local geometry, leading to better semantic representation and discrimination power.

IV. ANALYSIS OF CONVERGENCE

The iterative updating rules employed to minimize the objective function in LCCF have been rigorously demonstrated to be convergent. Our focus here is to explore the rate of convergence. Table 3 illustrates the convergence trajectories of NMF, CF, and LCCF across both datasets. In each plot, the y-axis represents the objective function value, while the x-axis denotes the iteration number. Notably, we observe rapid convergence of the multiplicative updating rules for all three algorithms, typically achieving convergence within 100 iterations.

TABLE 3.
CLUSTERING PERFORMANCE ON REUTERS-21578 (NORMALIZED MUTUAL INFORMATION)

k	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Avg.
KM	0.428	0.409	0.483	0.428	0.482	0.460	0.393	0.393	0.478	0.439
KM-NCW	0.627	0.630	0.655	0.525	0.572	0.522	0.454	0.464	0.540	0.554
AA	0.368	0.353	0.431	0.381	0.430	0.424	0.349	0.363	0.435	0.393
NC	0.596	0.584	0.586	0.500	0.552	0.508	0.434	0.441	0.524	0.525
NMF	0.436	0.410	0.509	0.424	0.485	0.449	0.362	0.391	0.464	0.437
NMF-NCW	0.608	0.641	0.626	0.533	0.576	0.545	0.461	0.471	0.556	0.558
CF	0.440	0.414	0.521	0.425	0.494	0.456	0.363	0.396	0.476	0.443
CF-NCW	0.605	0.648	0.631	0.534	0.582	0.549	0.466	0.475	0.550	0.560
LCCF	0.503	0.452	0.553	0.485	0.519	0.485	0.447	0.445	0.513	0.489
LCCF-NCW	0.599	0.652	0.668	0.556	0.623	0.601	0.538	0.533	0.567	0.593
following are	kernelized version of each algorithm with kernel function $(x_i, x_j)^2$									
KM	0.183	0.206	0.263	0.218	0.260	0.260	0.212	0.231	0.276	0.234
KM-NCW	0.509	0.590	0.539	0.446	0.506	0.468	0.424	0.412	0.474	0.485
AA	0.116	0.141	0.208	0.156	0.195	0.177	0.153	0.169	0.220	0.171
NC	0.490	0.517	0.528	0.433	0.504	0.479	0.442	0.437	0.458	0.476
CF	0.312	0.329	0.401	0.332	0.405	0.377	0.336	0.349	0.428	0.363
CF-NCW	0.567	0.529	0.488	0.446	0.484	0.490	0.528	0.472	0.427	0.492
LCCF	0.503	0.452	0.553	0.485	0.519	0.485	0.447	0.445	0.513	0.489
LCCF-NCW	0.648	0.640	0.677	0.576	0.632	0.591	0.566	0.544	0.583	0.606

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper has demonstrated the implementation and efficacy of Quantum Clustering techniques for static document sets, yielding promising results. While the current study focused on static environments using standard datasets, the potential of Quantum Clustering extends to dynamic environments such as web-based documents and industry databases. Future research can explore the adaptation of quantum clustering algorithms to dynamic environments, enhancing information retrieval and management systems. The proposed quantum clustering algorithm shows promise in improving clustering accuracy and facilitating faster browsing systems in today's digital landscape. By integrating semantic analysis, this novel clustering method can serve as a core technique in quantum computation, enabling the creation of diverse clusters tailored to specific contexts. Moreover, the paper introduces However, the parameter λ , which controls the smoothness of the LCCF model, poses challenges in model selection. Future research endeavours should focus on theoretically and efficiently determining the optimal value of λ to enhance the algorithm's performance.

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